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Influence of root characteristics on rice productivity in iron-rich lateritic soils of Kerala, India

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High iron (Fe) content and availability because of submergence and accumulation in the plant are suspected to be the reasons for low fertilizer responsiveness and yield of high-yielding genotypes in lateritic soils of Kerala, India. Since roots are the absorbing organs, their development is evidently an index of plant vigor. To study the influence of excess Fe on root characteristics and its relation to rice productivity, rice experiments were conducted at the Agricultural Research Station, Mannuthy, of Kerala Agricultural University during the 1995-96 and 1996-97 kharif seasons. The soil at the site was a lateritic sandy clay loam, acidic, and of medium fertility. Treatments consisted of three methods of crop establishment (dry seeding, wet seeding, and transplanting), two digging depths (15 and 30 cm), and three levels of farmyard manure (FYM) (0, 5, and 10 t ha⁻¹). Root characteristics and yields were recorded. Root Fe content was estimated.

Crop establishment significantly influenced root characteristics (Table 1). The dry-seeding treatment in which the plant grew for 40 d under dry soil conditions had the highest number of roots plant⁻¹ and average root length at the maximum tillering stage. Similarly, digging to a depth of 30 cm increased root number plant⁻¹. Raising the FYM levels increased the number of roots plant⁻¹ and average root length; the increases were statistically significant. Data also showed that the dry-seeding treatment had the highest grain

yield, with an improvement over wet seeding and transplanting of 37.8% and 40.8%, respectively.

Since different methods of crop establishment had uniform management practices, a high yield in the dry-seeded crop will mean higher nutrient-use efficiency than in other establishment methods. This can be explained on the basis of root characteristics, such as root number, average root length, and maximum root length.

The effectiveness of digging depth when viewed in the context of plant development showed that digging to a depth of 30 cm instead of 15 cm significantly increased yield. Increasing digging depth naturally increases the soil volume for root ramification and brings about leaching of Fe,

which in turn facilitates better nutrient absorption, plant growth, and yield.

Similarly, increasing FYM levels upped yield significantly. Here again increases in root number and other attributes were evident. This confirms that root characteristics are definite indices of productivity.

The correlation between root characteristics and biometric differentials with yield of rice (Table 2) showed that maximum correlation was observed in root number plant⁻¹ in terms of grain yield, straw yield, and total biomass followed by the difference in total dry weight between the flowering and panicle initiation (PI) stages. The difference in root dry weight between the PI and maximum tillering (MT) stages,

Table 1. Effect of cultural management on root characters and rice yield (pooled mean: 1995-96 and 1996-97).

Treatment ^a	Root no.	Maximum root length (cm)	Average root length (cm)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
				Grain	Straw	Total biomass
Crop establishment						
DSR	122.7	10.3	7.4	6.5	5.4	11.9
WSR	67.4	16.1	6.9	4.7	3.8	8.6
TPR	68.8	13.0	4.6	4.6	3.9	8.5
CD (0.05)	11.34	0.879	0.609	425.0	560.0	754.4
Digging						
D ₁₅	80.0	13.1	6.3	5.1	0.4	9.3
D ₃₀	92.16	13.2	6.2	5.5	4.5	10.0
CD (0.05)	9.16	ns	ns	347	ns	616.0
FYM						
M ₀	76.0	11.8	5.9	4.7	4.1	8.8
M ₅	82.2	13.1	6.2	5.4	4.5	10.0
M ₁₀	100.6	14.5	6.8	5.6	4.5	10.2
CD (0.05)	11.34	0.879	0.609	425	ns	754.4
CV (%)	19.30	9.86	14.26	8.81	13.98	8.54

^aDSR = dry-seeded rice, WSR = wet-seeded rice, TPR = transplanted rice, D₁₅ = 15-cm depth, D₃₀ = 30-cm depth, FYM = farmyard manure (M₀ = 0 t ha⁻¹, M₅ = 5 t ha⁻¹, M₁₀ = 10 t ha⁻¹).

Table 2. Correlation among root characters, root Fe content, and some biometric differentials with yield.

Root and biometric character	Yield			Root Fe content
	Grain	Straw	Total	
Shoot dry weight (PI-MT)	0.203	0.186	0.206	-
Root dry weight (PI-MT)	0.625**	0.631**	0.665**	-
Total dry weight (PI-MT)	0.422**	0.412	0.442**	-
Shoot dry weight (PI-MT)	0.609**	0.539**	0.610**	-
Root dry weight (FI-PI)	0.463**	0.494**	0.506**	-
Total dry weight (FI-PI)	0.629**	0.577**	0.640**	-
Root no. plant ⁻¹	0.748**	0.676**	0.757**	-0.607**
Av root length (cm)	0.402	0.358**	0.404**	-0.565**

PI = panicle initiation stage, MT = maximum tillering stage, FI = flowering stage. ** = significant at 0.01% level.

and the flowering and PI stages; shoot dry weight difference between the flowering and PI stages; total dry weight difference between the PI and MT stages; and average root length were also

highly correlated with grain yield, straw yield, and total biomass. The significant influence of average root length on yield demonstrated that average root length has a significant role in boosting yield.

A significant correlation observed between both root number and average root length and root iron content confirmed that Fe content and its deposition were the predisposing cause of low root development.

A correlation between biometric differentials and yield showed that root number plant⁻¹ at MT is the best index of future yield, which in turn suggests that inhibited root growth and/or decay is the best index of low yield of rice in lateritic soils.

Effects of temperature on fertility and seed set in intersubspecific hybrid rice

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Since intersubspecific hybrid rice showed strong heterosis in the past 12 years, many such hybrids were released for commercialization. However, some of them exhibited unstable seed set and limited grain yield under lower temperature. To use the strong heterosis in intersubspecific hybrids, it is necessary to study the reasons for their instability.

In this study, 11 intersubspecific hybrids, 1 indica hybrid, and 7 indica, japonica, or javanica inbred cultivars were used to investigate the effects of temperature on fertility and seed set, observe the variation in activity of male and female gametes, and look into suitable and safe temperatures (daily average) for the flowering stage.

All 11 intersubspecific hybrids, 2 indica cultivars, and 4 japonica or javanica cultivars showed a significant correlation between seed set and temperature. Results showed that the seed set of most rice hybrids and cultivars was sensitive to temperature, and that it was more sensitive in intersubspecific hybrids. When flowering within a temperature range of 13.7–29.3 °C (daily average), the seed set of intersubspecific hybrids would decrease by 6.74% ± 1.6% for each degree of temperature lower. This was significantly higher ($t = 3.14$, $n = 14$) than that of the four japonica or javanica cultivars (4.87% ± 2.7%).

Ten intersubspecific hybrids, two indica cultivars, and two japonica cultivars showed a significant correlation between pollen fertility and temperature. The pollen fertility of the 10 intersubspecific hybrids decreased by 3.42% ± 1.6% for each degree of temperature lower, was higher than that of the two japonica cultivars (1.40% ± 0.2%), and was close to that of the two indica cultivars (2.66% ± 2.9%).

The cross 3037/02428 (A172) exhibited a wide variation in spikelet fertility of 0–93% within a temperature range of 13.7–29.3 °C. The panicles, which flowered at 23.8 °C, showed a lower pollen fertility of 54.4% ± 14.9% for stained pollen grains; semifertile panicles were